

Book of Abstracts of the General Assembly 2019 (Porto, Portugal) of the

WECANet COST Action CA17105:

A pan-European Network for Marine Renewable Energy with a Focus on Wave Energy

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ISBN: 9789464000160

This publication is based upon work from the WECANet COST Action CA17105, supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology).

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Funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union

Reducing uncertainties on the long term power production of WECs

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Within the wide variety of marine renewable energy resources, wave energy appears as a promising, virtually untapped, alternative, with a lot of sites around the world with the potential of being exploited. On the other hand, there are some issues that must be addressed in detail so that wave energy becomes a fully-fledged renewable energy resource. Among them, the level of uncertainty in terms of long-term power production of Wave Energy Converters (WECs) stands out, which has been carried out primarily by the combination of resource and power matrices of WECs. In the field of wave resource characterisation, the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) has recently put forward a series of recommendations to develop a uniform methodology with the aim of ensuring consistency and accuracy in the wave resource characterisation: “IEC-62600-101 Marine energy – Wave, tidal and other water current converters – Part 101: Wave energy resource assessment and characterisation”. Overall, the IEC-62600-101 has proven to be a robust and coherent methodology, mainly intended for project and device developers, policy-makers and investors, which offers a set of recommendations related to the measurement, modelling, analysis and reporting of the wave energy resource, and the linkages between these activities.

However, and to the best knowledge of the authors, when estimating the long-term production of WECs no alternative standard to the power matrix method has been proposed, despite previous research has found that this methodology may produce results with levels of uncertainty close to 40%. In general, those uncertainties are related with the assumption of parametrical spectral shapes to compute the wave parameters (H_{m0} , T_p) that define the energy bins of wave resource power matrices. This fact appears to be significantly relevant for WECs with limited band frequency response (heaving bodies). Against the foregoing backdrop, this work aims to explore different alternatives to reduce uncertainties such as (i) construct power matrices assuming real spectrum shapes, (ii) consider resource power matrices for the spectrum peaks of fetch and wind sea, respectively and (iii) assess the effects of wave directionality in power production of WECs.

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